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ADVANTAGES OF OIL PALM PLANTATIONS AS CARBON SINK AND EMISSION-EFFICIENT OIL PRODUCTION

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RESUME

Oil palm plantations (and palm oil) are often accused as the main contributors to GHG emissions in the global agricultural sector. This accusation is considered misdirected because it does not match the FAO publication data (2022, 2023) which revealed that livestock farming and rice cultivation are still the main sub-sectors contributing to GHG emissions in the global agricultural sector. On the contrary, oil palm plantations produce palm oil which has low emissions and has great ability to absorb carbon emissions from the Earth's atmosphere (carbon sink) which are then stored as carbon stocks (carbon saving). In fact, the carbon sink capacity of oil palm plantations is higher than that of forests and other forest plants. This shows that oil palm plantations are an important part of the global climate change mitigation solution.

INTRODUCTION

The issues of [global warming](#) and [climate change](#) have been continuously discussed in the last few decades. The massive impact of global warming and climate change that threatens the existence of living things on Earth underscores the urgency for all parties to strive to find and work on solutions to reduce Green House Gas (GHG) emissions in the Earth's atmosphere.

The global palm oil industry holds significant potential as part of the solution to global climate change ([PASPI Monitor, 2023^a](#)). Apart from producing low-emission and sustainable bioenergy as an alternative substitute for emission-intensive fossil energy ([PASPI Monitor, 2023^b](#)), oil palm plantations also have the ability to absorb GHG emissions in the Earth's atmosphere.

On the other hand, oil palm plantations are accused as the main contributor to the increase in GHG emissions in the agricultural sector. Oil palm plantations are considered to be a significant source of carbon emissions (Germer and Sauerborn, 2007; Reijnders and Huijbregts, 2008; Chase and Henson, 2010; Carlson *et al.*, 2013). In addition to palm oil production process (farm-gate), the land use of oil palm plantations is also accused of being a major carbon emitter. In fact, these accusations were used as the basis for policies formulated by the European Union such as RED II ILUC ([PASPI Monitor, 2019](#)) and The Farm to Fork within the framework of the European Green Deal ([PASPI Monitor, 2021^a](#)).

This journal will discuss sub-sectors that contribute to the increase in GHG emissions in the global agricultural sector. Furthermore, it will also discuss the advantages of oil palm plantations in carbon sink and carbon saving, as well as emission-efficient oil production as part of mitigating global climate change.

GHG EMISSIONS OF GLOBAL AGRIFOOD SECTOR

Basically, all human activities produce GHG emissions. The agricultural sector is the second-largest contributor (after the energy sector) to global GHG emissions with a share of 18.4 percent (WRI, 2020; Olivier *et al.*, 2022; PASPI, 2023). With a broader approach, the latest publication of FAO (2023) revealed that the global agrifood system produced emissions totaling 16 Gt CO₂ eq in 2021. Emissions in the global agrifood system include farm-gate emissions related to the production process of agricultural and livestock products, land-use change emissions related to deforestation and drained organic soil for agricultural/livestock land, and emissions in pre-production (upstream sub-sector/production input) and post-production (downstream, transportation, household consumption, food product waste).

Of these three components in the global agrifood system, the largest GHG emissions were generated at the farm-gate level, amounting to 7.8 Gt CO₂ eq in 2021. This was followed by emissions from the pre- and post-production (5.3 Gt CO₂ eq) and emissions from land-use change (3.1 Gt CO₂ eq). Even though emissions at the farm-gate level are the largest, activities at the pre-and post-production levels produced emissions with the largest average increase during the 2001-2021 period, namely 48 percent (Figure 1). The average increase in farm-gate level emissions in that period was only 14 percent, while emissions from land-use change actually decreased by 19 percent.

Figure 1. Increase in GHG Emissions in the Global Agrifood System Based on Its Components for the 2001-2021 (Source: FAO, 2023)

At the farm-gate level (Figure 2) the largest emissions were produced by the global livestock sub-sector in 2021 amounting to 4.2 Gt CO₂ eq (54 percent), consisting of enteric fermentation (2.9 Gt CO₂ eq) and manure (1.3 Gt CO₂ eq). This was followed by drained organic soil and on-farm energy use, each at 0.9 Gt CO₂ eq (12 percent). Rice cultivation and use of synthetic fertilizers also fall into the sub-sectors/activities that generated the largest emissions at the farm-gate level, namely 0.7 Gt CO₂ eq (9 percent) and 0.6 Gt CO₂ eq (8 percent), respectively.

Figure 2. Sources of GHG Emissions in the Global Agrifood System at Farm-Gate Level in 2021 (Source: FAO, 2023)

Livestock products is the commodity that are produced with the highest emissions ([FAO, 2022](#)). The emissions contained in every one kilogram of cattle's meat 30 kg CO₂ eq. Then followed by sheep's meat (24.4 kg CO₂ eq/kg), sheep's milk (5.6 kg CO₂ eq/kg), pork/pig's meat (1.8 kg CO₂ eq/kg), cow's milk (1 kg CO₂ eq/kg), chicken's meat (0.6 kg CO₂ eq/kg), and eggs (0.6 kg CO₂ eq/kg). In addition to livestock products, emissions from one kilogram of rice reach 1 kg CO₂ eq.

The FAO publications (2022, 2023) above indicate that oil palm plantations and palm oil are not the main contributors to the increase in GHG emissions in the agricultural sector. Like the production of other agricultural commodities, the palm oil production process also generates emissions. The study by Harimurti *et al.* (2021) revealed that the average carbon emissions from production activities in oil palm plantations are 0.08 ton CO₂ eq/ton FFB/year. The greatest carbon emissions occur in 4-year-old plants (0.25 CO₂ eq/ton FFB) and then decrease to the lowest point at the age of 9 years-old plants (0.04 CO₂ eq/ton FFB).

Sources of emissions at the oil palm plantation and mill levels (Mathews and Ardiyanto, 2015) are POME (62 percent), fertilizer use (31.5 percent), and fossil energy use (5.1 percent). By improving management and adopting technology such as methane capture for processing POME, using palm biomass as substitute for fossil energy and anorganic fertilizer, and increasing productivity, emissions can be reduced in oil palm plantations and increase sustainability ([PASPI Monitor, 2021b](#); Alcock *et al.*, 2022).

CAPABILITY OF OIL PALM PLANTATIONS AS CARBON SINK AND SAVING

The global palm oil industry is one of industry that has the potential to be part of the solution for reducing global GHG emissions. Oil palm plantations are also often referred to as carbon plantations because they have important role in reabsorbing carbon from the Earth's atmosphere.

Similar to other plants worldwide, oil palm plants carry out the process of photosynthesis. Through this process, solar energy and carbon dioxide (CO₂) from the Earth's atmosphere are absorbed and transformed into palm oil, biomass, and some are stored in the form of carbon stocks. With the ability to absorb CO₂ from the Earth's atmosphere, oil palm plantations have a role as a carbon sink ([PASPI, 2023](#)).

Based on the study by Henson (1999), it was revealed that oil palm plantations absorb CO₂ (through photosynthesis) from the Earth's atmosphere by 161 tons of CO₂ per hectare and reuse (respiration) 96.5 tons of CO₂ per hectare. Thus, the net carbon sink for oil palm plants is 64.5 tons of CO₂ per hectare (Table 1).

Table 1. Oil Palm Plantations as a Carbon Sink

Indicator	Tropical Forest	Oil Palm Plantation
Gross assimilation (ton CO ₂ /ha/year)	163.5	161.0
Total respiration (ton CO ₂ /ha/year)	121.1	96.5
Net assimilation (ton CO ₂ /ha/year)	42.4	64.5
Oxygen production (ton O ₂ /ha/year)	7.09	18.70

Source: Henson (1999); PPKS (2004, 2005)

The carbon sink capacity of oil palm plantations is even greater than that of tropical forest. The study by Uning *et al.* (2020) also revealed the same thing, namely that oil palm plants absorb emissions by 64 tons of CO₂/hectare/year or higher compared to the capacity of forests (32 tons of CO₂/hectare/year). This can be understood considering that tropical forest are filled with mature/old plants, where the rate of photosynthesis has approached that of respiration (Soemarwoto, 1992).

IOPRI (2023) has summarized the results of empirical studies and also confirmed this. The carbon dioxide absorption capacity of oil palm plants (36 tons of CO₂ per hectare) is greater than that of natural forests (25 tons of CO₂ per hectare). The carbon sink capacity of oil palm plants is even

greater than that of forest plants such as mahogany (25 tons of CO₂ per hectare), teak (21 tons of CO₂ per hectare), pine (20 tons of CO₂ per hectare), and *seigon* (18 tons of CO₂ per hectare).

In the Academic Paper on Oil Palm as a Degraded Forest Plant prepared by the Faculty of Forestry IPB University and APKASINDO (Santosa *et al.*, 2023) by using Net Primary Production (NPP) shows oil palm plants have a higher value than tropical forests and other forest plants (such as acacia, pine, teak, eucalyptus). The NPP value indicates the total net carbon absorbed by plants from the atmosphere through the process of photosynthesis.

The study also compared the carbon dioxide absorption capacity of oil palm plants versus forests and forest plantations (Figure 3). Oil palm plants have an average carbon dioxide absorption of 51.9 Mg CO₂ eq/hectare/year, surpassing forests (51.1 tons of CO₂ eq/hectare/year) and forest plants.

Figure 3. Comparison of CO₂ Absorption Capacity between Palm Oil Versus Forests and Forest Plants (Source: Santosa *et al.*, 2023)

With indicators such as NPP values and carbon dioxide absorption in oil palm plants being relatively high, it indicates the significant capacity of oil palm plants as an absorber of carbon emissions. Supported by the characteristics of oil palm plants which are classified as annual plants (perennial plants) with an intensive root system, relatively large size, fast growth, and high production with a planting cycle (lifespan) of 25 years or more, oil palm plantations become a substantial “biological machine” for absorbing carbon dioxide CO₂.

In addition to its carbon absorption ability (carbon sink), oil palm plantations also have role in carbon storage (carbon saving). Through photosynthesis and the biosequestration process, the carbon absorbed by oil palm plants is converted into carbon stocks which are stored as biomass of the oil palm plant itself (above ground biomass) and in the underground root system (underground biomass) in the form of soil organic carbon and soil inorganic carbon (PASPL, 2023).

Chan's study (2002) calculated the amount of biomass and carbon stock (above ground biomass) resulting from carbon sequestration in oil palm plantations, ranging from 5.8 ton per hectare (on immature plants) to 45.3 ton per hectare (on plants aged 20-24 years), averaging 30 tons of carbon per hectare. Kusumawati *et al.* (2021) found that one-year-old oil palm plantations contain a carbon stock of 43.5 tons per hectare and 28-year-old oil palm plantations have a carbon stock of 74.7 tons per hectare. Khasanah's study (2019) also revealed that the average carbon stock in above ground biomass in Indonesia's oil palm plantations reached 40 tons per hectare.

The common thread from these various studies shows that the potential for carbon stocks in oil palm plantations continues to increase with increasing plant age. The carbon stock of oil palm plantations is an accumulation of the results of the process of absorbing CO₂ from the Earth's atmosphere, contributing to the reduction in CO₂ concentration in the Earth's atmosphere. This

further increases the potential for oil palm plantations to become part of the solution for mitigating global climate change.

Various studies (Gunarso *et al.*, 2013^{a,b}; Suharto *et al.*, 2019; [PASPI, 2023](#)) revealed that most of the origins of oil palm plantation land in Indonesia come from land cover with lower carbon stocks than oil palm plantations (excluding peatland oil palm plantations which is still a matter of debate). This means that land use change into oil palm plantations is a carbon absorption (net carbon sink) and not a carbon source. Apart from being part of climate change mitigation, the large carbon sink and carbon saving capacities inherent in oil palm plantations are part of afforestation (building “forest functions” outside forest areas) and rehabilitation of degraded/marginal land areas.

EMISSION-EFFICIENT VEGETABLE OIL PRODUCTION

At the beginning of this journal, it has been explained that the agricultural sector and the global agrifood system are among the major contributors to global GHG emissions. The implication is that several developed countries limit or even stop trading and consumption of agricultural commodities/products that are considered to contribute to the increase in GHG emissions, such as the European Union with the RED II ILUC ([PASPI Monitor, 2019](#)) and The Farm to Fork within the framework of the European Green Deal ([PASPI Monitor, 2021](#)). One of the agricultural commodities targeted by these policies is palm oil and its derivative products.

The arguments supporting these policies are considered to be misguided. Various empirical studies have actually proved the opposite. The studies by Beyer *et al.* (2020) and Beyer and Rademacher (2021) revealed that oil palm plantations produce the lowest-emission vegetable oil compared to other vegetable oil sources ([PASPI, 2023](#)). This means that palm oil emissions are lower compared to sunflower oil, rapeseed oil, olive oil, coconut oil, soybean oil, and peanut oil.

The study by Alcock *et al.* (2022) also revealed the same thing, namely that emissions (excluding land-use change emissions) in palm oil production are lower among the Top-4 main vegetable oil crops in the world. Every one kilogram of palm oil produced only generates emissions of 0.43 kg CO₂. Meanwhile, the emissions resulting from the production of one kilogram of soybean oil, sunflower oil, and rapeseed oil are 1.18 kg CO₂, 1.13 kg CO₂, and 1.02 kg CO₂, respectively.

The results of this study also proved that the “Palm Oil Free” policy or movement as a pro-environment which aims to limit/stop palm oil consumption is actually an anti-environment movement. Avoiding global consumption of palm oil will actually lead to worse environmental impacts, namely an increase in GHG emissions from the production of vegetable oils that are more emission-intensive. If the global community is concerned about reducing GHG emissions, it should avoid consuming emission-intensive agricultural commodities such as meat, milk, and eggs or soybean oil, rather than avoiding the consumption of palm oil which is relatively emission efficient.

CONCLUSION

The agricultural sector and global agrifood system are the second-largest contributors (after energy) to global GHG emissions. Based on this fact, various parties accuse oil palm plantations and palm oil as the main contributors to GHG emissions in the global agricultural sector. The implication of this argument is the emergence of the “Palm Oil Free” movement and importing countries' policies that limit or even stop the trade and consumption of palm oil (and its derivative products) as a measure to reduce GHG emissions and mitigate global climate change.

The anti-palm oil movement or policies that discriminate against palm oil are considered misdirected. FAO publications (2022, 2023) revealed that livestock and rice cultivation are the main sub-sectors generating GHG emissions in the global agricultural sector. The publications also stated that livestock commodities (meat, milk, eggs) and rice are the agricultural commodities with the largest emission. On the other hand, oil palm plantations, which have been the “scapegoat” as the main contributor to GHG emissions in the global agricultural sector. Instead, they are actually able to produce the most emission-efficient vegetable oil compared to other vegetable oils.

Another advantage that oil palm plantations have is their ability to act as a carbon sink and carbon saving. The ability of oil palm plants to absorb carbon dioxide from the Earth's atmosphere (carbon sink) is even greater than the ability of forests and other forest plants. The carbon from the Earth's atmosphere is then absorbed and stored as carbon stocks (carbon saving), where the volume of the carbon stocks will continue to increase as its plant age increases. This demonstrates the enormous potential of oil palm plantations, not only as producer of emission-efficient vegetable oil, but also as part of the solution for mitigating global climate change.

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